

Article

Put on a open (max 2) or closed (max 1)
Project on the table

Fame for writer: 2

Fame for Project
owner: 1

Article

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Papermill Article

This Article does
not require a
Project

Fame 3

Plagiarism

Substitute an Article
written by another
player with this card.
-2 Fame for the
other player.

Fame 3

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